

A scoping review of mother-child separation in clinical paediatric settings

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Abstract

There is increasing evidence to suggest that autonomic regulation of hospitalised infants is affected by separation from their mother. This review explored the extent of the evidence relating to the impact of separation on infants and children, and aimed to identify suitable measures of the impact of mother-child separation. We conducted a scoping review of seven databases using the main search terms “physiological”, “psychological”, “infant/child”, “maternal separation” and “hospital”. Thirty-four papers containing data relevant to the effects of mother-child separation on either member of the pair were included. Findings highlight the central importance of the mother's presence in mediating the stressful effects of hospitalisation on her child. The majority of papers reported on psychological effects of separation on mothers of infants, or on younger children. We identified no papers reporting on physiological effects on the older child or mothers of older children, or psychological effects on mothers of older children. Only nine papers used validated tools to measure the effects of separation. There is a need for more evidence, based on validated measurement, about the psychological effects of separation on the child, particularly the older child, and on the physiological effects of separation on the mother-child pair during hospitalisation.

Keywords: Child, hospital, infant, mother-child, separation, stress physiological, stress psychological

Introduction

Hospitalisation during childhood is recognised as a stressful healthcare event (Schoore, 2000). While maternal presence has long been valued in many paediatric care settings (Davies, 2010), evidence suggests that the presence of the mother is highly relevant to the autonomic regulation of hospitalised infants, and possibly older babies and children (Bergman, 2014).

In recent years, new knowledge from the fields of developmental psychology and infant mental health has confirmed the important regulatory function of maternal presence

(Schore, 2005). In the neurosciences, advanced imaging and validated measures of autonomic nervous system (ANS) responses have enhanced understanding of the interrelationships between the ANS of the mother and the child (Bergman et al., 2004; Morgan et al., 2011). These emerging knowledge bases are contributing important new understandings which have not yet changed the way that children are cared for, or the way that research into paediatric care is conducted.

Our unit focuses on training children's nurses and understanding and developing the clinical practice of children's nurses in Africa. One such recent exploration of clinical practice investigated the impact of maternal presence on infants at a tertiary care facility in southern Africa by measuring the infant's heart rate variability (HRV) and cardiac impedance (Ssenyonga et al., 2014). The sample was under-powered and researchers were unable to control for the many variables in a clinical practice setting but cautiously concluded that the results pointed towards ameliorating effects of maternal presence on infant autonomic dysregulation. Researchers inferred that infants experience separation intensely, and that this can be detected through objective measurement of observable ANS parameters. To make further progress with research into this phenomenon it was determined that further suitable measures of the impact of mother-child separation needed to be identified. We also wanted to scope existing evidence relating to the impact of maternal separation on older babies and children.

A preliminary search for previous reviews on this topic in the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) database of systematic reviews and implementation reports and the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews identified a small number of reviews which addressed related topics, but none that exactly addressed the questions of interest to us. Our preliminary searching identified a number of discussion/review papers looking at various aspects of mother-child separation and these have been included in the results. We did not find any reviews focusing on the separation of the mother and her older infant/child and none that focused on the possible ameliorating effect of the mother's presence on the child's physiology, particularly during illness. Our review extends the summary of evidence beyond the newborn period, focusing on the degree of separation of the mother-child pair in the context of hospitalisation and the reported physiological and psychological effects of the separation on the pair.

Aim

To identify existing evidence in relation to separation of the mother-child pair in clinical paediatric settings. Our specific questions were: (1) What are the contexts in which the mother-child pair are described as being separated? (2) What are the reported physiological and psychological effects of separation on the mother and child? (3) What tools are being used to measure the effects of separation? (4) What are the gaps in the knowledge base?

Method

A scoping review was performed to identify, select and combine the results of multiple papers. Scoping reviews offer particular strengths as an exploratory review method when it is suspected that substantial gaps in both research and general knowledge exist (Peters et al., 2015), and can be a helpful first step in investigating what research has been done in a field and what other knowledge exists (Colquhoun et al., 2014).

The preferred reporting instructions for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) statement, endorsed by the JBI, was consulted as a rigour guide to ensure transparency and replicability of the process while limiting bias – see Figure 1 (Moher et al., 2009; Peters et al., 2017). The inclusion criteria were based on the elements of population (*mothers and infants/children*); concept (*separation*) and context (*in hospital*). Limits applied to the search were: publication date (January 2003 to June 2018), publications in English age of child (infants: 0 to 23 months, children: 2 to 12 years, as per MeSH term definitions) and publications about humans. A 15-year period was defined to ensure inclusion of the most recent research on this topic, informed by researchers' knowledge of relevant sources exploring impact measurement of mother-child separation (Peters et al., 2017). Following consultation with a health sciences librarian, a search was conducted across seven databases: PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, CINAHL, PsychInfo, Africa wide and Psych articles. The five main areas searched were: "physiological", "psychological", "infant/child", "maternal separation" and "hospital". Google Scholar was searched for any grey literature on the topic. A limitation to this search strategy was the large amount of irrelevant papers that were retrieved due to the broad search terms and the time consuming process involved in screening these. Papers were first screened by title, then abstract. The full-texts were retrieved for all potentially relevant papers and each was read by any two of the authors. Discrepancies regarding the inclusion of a paper were discussed among the authors and resolved. Only results relevant to the effects of separation on the mother-child pair were extracted. Data were not limited to any type of variable or study methodology. Papers were only excluded if they did not report on the effects of separation in hospital. A qualitative approach to synthesis was followed to allow for variations in samples and methodologies. The reporting guidelines for scoping reviews produced by The JBI were adhered to (Peters et al., 2017).

We did not identify a consistent definition of separation in the papers we reviewed. We therefore defined the concept of separation *a priori* as the mother-child pair not being together. We defined the physiological effects on the child and mother as outcomes that relate to the body, relating to tangible, concrete entities that are perceived through the senses and measurable through empirical tools. Psychological effects were defined as outcomes that arise in the mind and that are related to the emotional state of the pair.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow Diagram

Results

The search strategy revealed 1,473 papers of which a high proportion (n=1,342) were irrelevant because they dealt with separation outside hospital. Abstracts were retrieved for 131 papers and an additional 32 irrelevant papers were identified, resulting in the retrieval of 73 full-texts. Following a co-review process, a further 37 papers were excluded, resulting in a sample of 36. A Cochrane review written by Moore et al (2016) included two intervention studies that were found in the database search (Bergman et al., 2004; Nolan and Lawrence, 2009) and the results from these studies are therefore not discussed further. The final sample therefore comprised 34 papers. See PRISMA diagram (Figure 1) for search results. Relevant data were extracted and tabulated according to descriptive studies, intervention studies and review/discussion-type papers (Appendix 1: Tables 1 to 3). Study participants included mothers, infants and children. Five papers included parents and not mothers only. Two of these papers (Koller et al., 2006 and Kerr et al., 2017) report results of interviews with parents and one review paper (Boykova 2016) included parents collectively. Reported results did not separate mother results from fathers, hence they were not excluded. The remaining two studies (Alves et al., 2016; Sankar et al., 2017) explored the effects of separation on breastfeeding and these extracted results therefore relate to mothers only. Reference lists of included papers were scanned for any additional sources of evidence. No additional papers were added. Results are reported under the main contributions made to the knowledge on the effects of separation on the mother-child pair. Findings related to the fourth review question (What are the gaps in the knowledge base?) are reported in the summary section under each category and are later discussed collectively prior to the conclusion.

Contexts of separation

Analysis resulted in the identification of three main contextual categories:

- Separation of newborn infants and their mothers (n= 7)
- Separation due to either the mother or the infant being admitted to intensive/special care (n= 25)
- Separation due to care practices (n= 2)

Many different forms of mother-child separation were described, spanning a variety of healthcare settings and we found little consistency in the way that the concepts of 'separation' or 'presence' were applied.

The contexts of separation are used to structure presentation of the remaining results. For each contextual category, findings are presented in relation to the next two review questions, i.e. (2) What are the reported physiological and psychological effects of separation on the child and the mother? and (3) What tools are being used to measure the effects of separation? Question (4) What are the gaps in the knowledge base? is discussed at the end of the results.

Separation of newborn infants and their mothers

The extent of separation reported in this context varied between zero separation due to continuous skin-to-skin contact or breastfeeding, to brief separation of the mother-child pair.

Effects of separation (child, physiological)

Moore et al. (2016) published a Cochrane systematic review of trials to assess the effects of immediate or early skin-to-skin contact on healthy newborn infants and their mothers compared to standard contact, i.e. infants held swaddled or dressed in their mother's arms, placed in open cribs or under radiant warmers. The infants in skin-to-skin contact had better stabilization on three physiological parameters as measured by the SCRIP tool, a validated measure of stability of the cardiorespiratory system in preterm infants, higher blood glucose levels and similar temperatures to infants in standard care (Moore et al., 2016).

Four other intervention studies were identified that reported on the physiological effects of separation on the infant. In two of these studies (Mörelus et al., 2005; Morgan et al., 2011) the subjects served as their own controls, with comparison of infants' physiological outcomes in skin-to-skin contact with their mothers and sleeping alone. In Mörelus et al.'s (2005) study infants' salivary cortisol, heart rate, oxygen saturations and pain levels were measured during and after skin-to-skin contact on two out of four occasions (first and fourth skin-to-skin contact). The infants' physiological response showed a decrease in pain scores and heart rate during skin-to-skin contact, cortisol levels were higher at the first skin-to-skin contact than at the fourth indicating clinical stabilisation, they were more relaxed and had a deeper sleep as reflected by their heart rate and behavioural state (Mörelus et al., 2005). Morgan et al. (2011) measured infants' level of arousal and HRV. Results revealed that separation, i.e. no skin-to-skin contact, was associated with a dramatic increase in HRV power and had a negative impact on quiet sleep duration (Morgan et al., 2011). Chi Luong et al. (2016) compared the effects of skin-to-skin contact and the conventional method of care in Vietnam which involves separation of the mother and her low birth-weight infant. In a large cohort (n=100), measures of the infants' physiological stabilization were the SCRIP score and blood glucose levels (Chi Luong et al., 2016). Results revealed a significantly greater SCRIP score in the skin-to-skin contact group at 120min (5.66 ± 0.72 vs 4.72 ± 0.83 , $p < 0.0001$) and 360min (5.82 ± 0.66 vs 5.24 ± 0.72 , $p = 0.0001$). Infants in skin-to-skin contact required significantly less IV fluids (9/50 vs 26/50 $p < 0.001$) and antibiotics (9/50 vs 25/50, $p = 0.004$), while separated infants experienced bradycardia, decreased respiratory rates, lower temperatures and blood glucose levels (Chi Luong et al., 2016).

Other infant physiological outcomes reported in the intervention studies were pain scores during heel lance (infants breastfed and in skin-to-skin contact, infants given sucrose and in skin-to-skin contact, infants in skin-to-skin contact and infants given glucose) (Gabriel et al., 2013). Gabriel et al. (2013) found that breastfed infants in skin-to-skin contact was

associated with significantly lower pain scores compared to other forms of non-pharmaceutical analgesia tested.

In a review paper by Groer et al. (2015) the authors described current understandings of the nature of the microbiome of the very low birth-weight infant. Factors that influence the infant's microbiome include caesarean section delivery, antibiotic use, breastfeeding and skin-to-skin contact (Groer et al., 2015). The authors recommend that use of the mother's own milk should be a priority, antibiotics should be used only when essential and separation from the mother should be avoided as skin-to-skin contact is essential to microbial transfer (Groer et al., 2015).

Effects of separation (mother, physiological)

Only one study (Mörelus et al., 2005) reported physiological effects on the mother. Mörelus et al. (2005) reported a decrease in maternal salivary cortisol and heart rate during skin-to-skin contact.

Effects of separation (mother, psychological)

Mörelus et al. (2005) also investigated how skin-to-skin contact influenced the stress of the mothers (n=17) measured by a visual analogue scale (VAS). The results showed the highest stress score immediately prior to the first skin-to-skin contact which decreased by 89% following the mothers contact with her infant.

Another context in which the psychological benefits of skin-to-skin contact and not being separated has been highlighted as important is for mothers of stillborn infants (Lindgren et al., 2014). When mothers were interviewed they expressed that leaving the infant at the hospital goes against a mother's biological instinct to care for and protect her infant and described their identity as mothers being demolished at the time of separation (Lindgren et al., 2014).

Measures of effects

Five studies reported on the physiological effects of separation, as measured through empirical tools (Chi Luong et al., 2016; Gabriel et al., 2013; Moore et al., 2016; Mörelus et al., 2005; Morgan et al., 2011), including infant heart rate, respiratory rate, oxygen saturations, blood glucose, level of arousal, cardiac inter-beat intervals, salivary cortisol and HRV. Maternal physiological measures included cortisol level and heart rate. Maternal psychological measures of mood and stress were measured by validated tools (Mörelus et al., 2005).

One study used interviews to elicit mothers' reports of the effects of separation (Lindgren et al., 2014).

Summary

The results of infant physiological outcomes presented by validated measures indicate better overall physiological outcomes when infants are in skin-to-skin contact. The

psychological effects on the mother reported through validated tools and interviews highlight a better mood state when mothers are in skin-to-skin contact with their infants. The results highlight the importance of skin-to-skin contact for the health and welfare of the pair.

Separation due to either the mother or the infant being admitted to intensive/special care

Papers related to this context involved the greatest extent of separation of the mother-child pair. Most (25/34) of the papers included in the review are reported here.

Effects of separation (child, physiological)

D'Agata et al. (2016) published a research synthesis of Infant Medical Trauma in neonatal intensive care units (NICU) (IMTN). The authors describe how the combination of parental separation, stress and pain contribute negatively to the infant's allostatic load, increasing vulnerability and the risk for poorer outcomes subsequently (D'Agata et al., 2016).

In a repeated measures randomised controlled trial conducted by Dearn and Shoemark (2014), infants' behavioural state, oxygen saturation and heart rate were measured during exposure to lullaby music with and without their mothers. Infants' physiological and behavioural regulation were affected by the presence and departure of their mothers, displaying an increase in oxygen saturations when mothers were present (CI 0.12 to 1.40), despite mothers not interacting with the infant for most of the time when present. Infants spent less time in quiet sleep when separated from their mothers. There was no significant independent effect of music on the infants (Dearn and Shoemark, 2014).

Effects of separation (child, psychological)

Only one study (Pennestri et al., 2015) explored the psychological effects of separation on the infant. Pennestri et al. (2015) measured the difference in attachment security at 36 months between children who received special care in NICU or in an incubator at birth and children who did not. Logistic regression revealed an odds ratio of 6.1 for developing disorganised attachment after a stay in NICU, when controlling for confounding variables (CI 1.76 to 21.02). However, the degree of separation of the mother-child pair during NICU is not clear (Pennestri et al., 2015).

Effects of separation (mother, physiological)

Several papers which reported on the effect of separation on breastfeeding are included here as the physiological process of breastmilk production and demand are linked to the effects of separation. Mylod (2015) discussed current understandings in relation to breastfeeding hospitalised children, highlighting the links between exclusive breastfeeding, aided by the presence of the mother, and the prevention and reduction of myriad infections and conditions (Mylod, 2015). Skin-to-skin contact facilitates breastfeeding yet the separation of the mother-child pair for assessment, stabilisation and transfer to specialist care impedes the initiation of breastfeeding (Mylod, 2015).

Mothers described ambivalent attitudes towards expressing breastmilk (Hurst et al., 2013, Sankar et al., 2017). Mothers felt that expressing breastmilk was therapeutic and represented a practical act of caring for their infants (Hurst et al., 2013, Ikonen et al., 2016). The majority of mothers felt separation from their infant hindered milk supply (Alves et al., 2016; Chaplin et al., 2016; Ikonen et al., 2016). The determination of mothers to breastfeed their infants was evident in a study by Mukwenda et al. (2017) where mothers who had been admitted to ICU to recover from eclampsia negotiated stairs every three hours in order to reach the nursery (Mukwenda et al., 2017).

Effects of separation (mother, psychological)

Negative impacts of separation on mothers' emotional states were widely reported. de Macedo et al. (2007) measured mothers' mood variation before and after visiting their infants in NICU. Mothers who engaged in kangaroo-mother-care reported more positive mood states than mothers whose infants were nursed in incubators and these differences were accounted for by prolonged contact with the infant (de Macedo et al., 2007).

The separation of the mother-child pair was associated with emotional chaos, anxiety, stress, distress, deep loss, sadness and a yearning to be together (Bayes et al., 2012; Chaplin et al., 2016; Elmir et al., 2012; Flacking et al., 2006; Gulla et al., 2017; Lindberg and Öhrling, 2008; Mukwenda et al., 2017; Wigert et al., 2006). Mothers of preterm infants reported a sense of loss for their full-term infant (Flacking et al., 2006), emptiness at no longer being pregnant (Baum et al., 2012), and unprepared for the NICU experience (Wigert et al., 2006). Mothers felt uncertainty with regard to who was looking after their infant (Hammarlund et al., 2012; Elmir et al., 2012; Mukwenda et al., 2017; Wigert et al., 2006) and worry over their infant's health (Akbarbegloo et al., 2013; Lindberg and Öhrling, 2008). Mothers were stressed about separation and not being able to help or protect their infant from painful procedures (Akbarbegloo et al., 2013).

In an intervention study by Kerr et al. (2017), real-time images of the infant were transmitted via webcam from the neonatal unit to the mother's bedside. Parents reported an enhanced feeling of closeness and emotional wellbeing with technology bridging the gap of separation by providing visual proximity to their infant (Kerr et al., 2017).

Nelson's (2003) meta-synthesis identified the basic process of maternal transition as centring on mothers experiencing the presence of their child and being involved in their care. Mothers found the transition to motherhood a struggle when their infants were admitted to NICU (Akbarbegloo et al., 2013; Baum et al., 2012; Flacking et al., 2006; Hurst et al., 2013; Lindberg and Öhrling, 2008; Shin and White-Traut, 2007) and when separated from their infants due to their own incapacitation following surgery (Bayes et al., 2012; Chaplin et al., 2016; Elmir et al., 2012). Mothers lamented lost bonding time with their infant and the interruption to their new mothering role (Baum et al., 2012; Bayes et al., 2012; Chaplin et al., 2016; Elmir et al., 2012; Flacking et al., 2006; Hurst et al., 2013; Lindberg and Öhrling, 2008; Shin and White-Traut, 2007). Greater time spent with their infant and higher levels of involvement in their care contributed to more secure parenting

identities for mothers (Flacking et al., 2006; Lindberg and Öhring, 2008). The results of Akbarbegloo et al.'s (2013) PSS administered to 300 mothers revealed that the subscale of "relationship with baby and parental role" scored significantly higher than the subscales of "NICU environment" and "how the baby looks, behaves and treatment" as a source of maternal stress (mean rank 2.11 vs 1.98 and 1.91, $p=0.047$).

Separation of a mother from her newborn baby due to NICU admission affects neurobiology associated with the initial bonding period (Boykova, 2016; Olza-Fernández et al., 2014). In Olza-Fernández et al.'s (2014) review, the authors discuss the hormonal cascade in the maternal and infant brain at parturition, the early postpartum period and lactation which prime the mother for initiation and consolidation of attachment. Elicitation of neuroendocrine changes associated with mother-infant synchrony essential to the initial bonding process are impaired by separation, with long-term effects on mother-child interaction and patterns of mothering (Olza-Fernández et al., 2014). Boykova's (2016) review highlights lost initial bonding time, mothers not feeling like a mother and the risk for the mother-child pair developing strained relationships (Boykova, 2016).

Measures of effects

Very few papers ($n=9$) reported physiological effects of separation, and only one study (Dearn and Shoemark, 2014) used validated tools to record infants' physiological measures of separation. Two studies (Akbarbegloo et al., 2013; de Macedo et al., 2007) used validated measures of mothers' psychological effects of separation. Mothers' psychological effects of separation were elicited through structured questionnaires (Ikonen et al., 2016), semi-/structured interviews (Baum et al., 2012; Bayes et al., 2012; Elmir et al., 2012; Flacking et al., 2006; Hurst et al., 2013; Lindberg and Öhring, 2008; Mukwenda et al., 2017; Wigert et al., 2006), interviews and journal writing (Chaplin et al., 2016), protocol writing (Hammarlund et al., 2012) and focus groups (Gulla et al., 2017). Three studies interviewed mothers and fathers (Alves et al., 2016; Kerr et al., 2017; Sankar et al., 2017), two of which explored the effects of separation on mothers' breastfeeding (Alves et al., 2016; Sankar et al., 2017) and one explored the effects of video technology bridging the gap of separation on parents.

Summary

The effects of intermittent or prolonged separation of the mother-child pair due to either of them requiring intensive/specialist care are widely reported. However, only one paper reported the positive physiological effects on the infant if the mother is present, with or without skin-to-skin contact, and only one paper reported on the longer-term negative psychological effect on the infant due to separation during this time. The effects on the mother are vastly reported and include the battle to establish and maintain breastfeeding and the emotional struggles regarding negative mood states and transitioning to motherhood.

Separation due to care practices

In this context, separation of the mother-child pair occurred because mothers could not/did not room in with their hospitalised children (Coyne, 2006) or children were nursed in isolation (Koller et al., 2006). Only results relating to the psychological effects of separation were found and reported.

Effects of separation

Older children (ages 7 to 14, n=11) voiced concerns when separated from their families and indicated that their parents played an important role in ameliorating the negative aspects of hospitalisation (Coyne, 2006). This was echoed by children in a study by Koller et al. (2006) who were nursed in isolation. The children in this study were lonely, worried about other family members and felt they were being punished (Koller et al., 2006).

Mothers and fathers separated from their hospitalised children have reported feelings of helplessness at not being able to look after their children and felt frustrated by their lack of control (Koller et al., 2006).

Measures of effect

Only interviews were used in this context and no validated tools. These included semi-structured interviews with children (Coyne, 2006) and in-depth interviews with children and their parents (Koller et al., 2006).

Summary

The two studies identified, reported on the negative psychological effects of separation.

As highlighted in Table 4, 9/34 papers reported on the use of validated tools to measure the physiological and/or psychological effects of mother-child separation. The majority (7/9) of these investigated physiological effects. All seven reported on physiological effects on infants, with one also reporting on physiological effects on mothers of infants. Only 4/23 papers which reported on psychological effects used validated measures, one measuring effects on infants, and three measuring effects on mothers.

Table 4. Summary of validated measures

Child physiological effects		Child psychological effects	
<i>Moore et al. 2016</i> (Cochrane Systematic Review)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCRIP stability of cardio-respiratory system in preterm infants 	<i>Pennestri et al. 2015</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strange Situation Procedure to measure security attachment
<i>Mörelus et al. 2005</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salivary cortisol • Heart rate • NIPP Neonatal Infant Pain Profile • NIPS Neonatal Infant Pain Scale 		
<i>Morgan et al. 2011</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anderson Behavioural State Scale • Inter-beat intervals • Heart rate variability 		
<i>Gabriel et al. 2013</i> <i>Dearn et al. 2014</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NIPS • Thoman's primary states taxonomy for behavioural state • SPO2 • Heart rate 		
<i>Chi Luong et al. 2016</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCRIP • Blood glucose 		
Mother physiological effects		Mother psychological effects	
<i>Mörelus et al. 2005</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salivary cortisol • Heart rate 	<i>Mörelus et al. 2005</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mood scale • Stress visual analogue scale
		<i>Akbarbegloo et al. 2013</i> <i>de Macedo et al. 2007</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PSS:NICU parent stressor scale • Visual analogue mood scale

Only nine out of 34 items reported on the use of validated tools to measure the physiological and/or psychological effects of mother-child separation.

Discussion

All the evidence reported in this review indicates negative effects of separating the mother-child pair. As this is a scoping review, no formal appraisal of quality or bias was conducted. It is possible that design bias, selective reporting or publication bias may be distorting the literature on this topic. However, when considered in the context of long-established research into attachment theory (Ainsworth, 1978, Bowlby, 1979) and the new knowledge emerging from the rapidly expanding fields of social neuroscience and interpersonal

neurobiology (Blakemore et al., 2004, Siegel, 2001), the evidence identified is consistent with current understandings.

The familiar attachment patterns of protest, despair and detachment that are visible in young children separated from their mothers are now understood to result from the loss of regulatory functions that would otherwise be provided through the mother's presence (Schoore, 2000). There is evidence that children and care-givers physiologically regulate one another through social interaction, affecting both immediate physiological status and longer-term brain structure (Carpendale and Lewis, 2004). The principle that separation of the mother-child pair during stressful healthcare events results in harmful effects of dysregulation and subsequent epigenetic changes underlies the clinical practice models of Zero Separation (Bergman, 2014), Kangaroo-Mother-Care (World Health Organisation, 2003) and skin-to-skin contact (Moore et al., 2016).

The profile of publications from the previous 15 years suggests that practices resulting in separation persist in many forms and across a full range of healthcare settings. Our review did not aim to identify factors which contributed to mother-child separation. However, we noted that organisational and environmental factors which prevented mothers from being close to their children were widely and consistently documented (Baum et al., 2012; Gulla et al., 2017; Mukwenda et al., 2017; Wigert et al., 2006). These descriptions align with the wider literature on this topic, which suggests that despite an increasingly consistent evidence base, facilitation of parental presence remains an inconsistent and hesitant practice (Suresh and Crowe, 2012; Farah et al., 2007; Gillis and Rennick, 2006).

What are the gaps in the knowledge base?

Our review suggests that the evidence base regarding physiological effects of separation on the mother-child pair during hospitalisation is far from comprehensive. We did find recent contributions which suggest that separation of the mother-child pair would negatively impact the beneficial process of microbial transfer from mother to child (Groer et al., 2015; Mylod, 2015), which is an interesting research direction. The absence of any papers reporting on physiological effects of children older than infants suggests that further research into the physiological effects of separation on the mother and hospitalised child, especially older children, is required.

Based on our findings we consider that saturation of the psychological effects on mothers has been achieved. There is a need for more evidence about the psychological effects of separation on the child, particularly the older child, obtained through the use of validated tools.

Just over half of the studies investigating physiological effects (8/15) used non-validated measures. The majority of the psychological effects were obtained through observational studies and qualitative research. We believe that these effects are indicative of the physiological state and ANS response of the mother-child pair, but this has not been demonstrated in the literature.

Implications for practice

Practitioners delivering health services for children should ensure that the increasingly consistent evidence of harmful effects of separation of the mother-child pair informs institutional policies and healthcare practices. Practitioners should actively identify institutional barriers and practices that prevent the pair from being together, particularly during stressful healthcare events.

Recommendations for future research

Published outputs from the previous 15 years reveal a lack of integration between research into the psychology and physiology of separation. We suggest that research which integrates these two areas of inquiry through the application of social neuroscience and interpersonal neurobiology, and which uses appropriate validated empirical measures of ANS response to presence and separation, will be of value.

Conclusion

Highlights of this scope review include a comprehensive search strategy and the inclusion of different study designs that spanned 15 years of research. It synthesised the results of 34 papers that reported on the effects of mother-child separation on the mother and child in the context of paediatric clinical settings. We conclude that the current literature consistently underlines the central importance of the mother's presence in mediating the stressful effects of hospitalisation on her child. Separation of the mother-child pair in hospital constitutes a harmful event and should be avoided as much as possible.

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Declaration of Conflicting Interests

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Tables 1 to 3 – A scoping review of mother-child separation in clinical paediatric settings

Table 1. Summary of evidence from descriptive studies

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Methodology	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2006 Coyne, I. <i>England</i>	Paediatric ward	To elicit children's experiences of hospitalisation to identify stressful events	7 to 14-year old children (N = 11. 8 chronically ill and 3 acutely ill).	Grounded theory	Semi-structured in-depth interviews	Children regard their parents' presence as important in ameliorating the negative aspects of hospitalisation.
2006 Flacking R, Ewald U, Nyqvist K, Starrin B. <i>Sweden</i>	Neonatal units and NICU	To explore the emotional experience of the BF process for mothers of very premature infants.	Mothers of very preterm infants <32wks (N=25)	Qualitative study using a grounded theory approach	Retrospective semi-structured interviews, within 3-17 month of birth	Separation from their premature infant resulted in negative experiences for the mother related to feelings of loss and interrupted the transition to 'becoming a mother'.
2006 Wigert, H. Johansson, R. Berg, M. Hellstrom, AL. <i>Sweden</i>	NICU	To describe mothers' experiences when their full-term newborn child was cared for in a NICU during the postpartum maternity care period.	Mothers (N=10)	Phenomenological hermeneutic	Retrospective narrative interviews	Mothers felt excluded from their child's care and worried about whether their child was being cared for without them. Mothers described negative feelings resulting from 'exclusion' from the NICU including fear, guilt, anxiety, loneliness and a sense of not belonging.

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Methodology	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2006 Koller, DF. Nicholas, DB. Goldie, RS. Gearing, R. Selkirk, EK. <i>Canada</i>	Paediatric isolation	To examine the experiences and perspectives of children, their parents and paediatric HCP	Hospitalised children with probable or suspected SARS (N=5), their parents (N=10), and HCP who took care of them (N=8) – <i>HCP data not included in results</i>	Ethnographic qualitative	In-depth ethnographic interviews and hospital record review	Children were lonely, worried about other family members and felt they were being punished. Separation anxiety continued after hospitalisation. Parents expressed discomfort at not being able to care for their children and were frustrated by their lack of control.
2007 de Macedo, EC. Cruvinel, F. Lukasova, K. D'Antino, MEF. <i>Brazil</i>	NICU	To compare the mood variation of mothers enrolled in a KMC program to that of mothers with infants in conventional incubator care.	Mothers of infants (N= 90. 30 term infants, 30 preterm infants and 30 infants in KMC.)	Quantitative, descriptive Group comparison	VAMS	Significant positive post-visit mood variation observed in mothers of KMC infants. Mothers in KMC sessions (vs incubator) reported positive mood variation: feeling calmer, stronger, well-coordinated, energetic, contented, tranquil, quick-witted, relaxed, proficient, happy, friendly and clear-headed. Significant negative post-visit mood variations observed in mothers of incubator-care infants. Mothers reported an increase in only one measure: feeling clumsy.
2007 Shin, H. White-Traut, R. <i>Korea</i>	NICU	To analyse the concept of transition to motherhood.	Mothers with infants in NICU (N=15)	Qualitative descriptive	Interviews	Separation due to neonates' admission to NICU diminished or distanced the maternal role, resulting in diminished interaction.

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Methodology	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2008 Lindberg, B. Öhring, K. <i>Sweden</i>	NICU	To describe mothers' experience of having a prematurely born infant.	Mothers (N=6)	Descriptive qualitative	Retrospective open-ended interviews	Separation from the infants was the most stressful part of having a preterm birth and mothers in the study wanted to be close to the infant as much as possible.
2011 Elmir, R. Schmied, V. Wilkes, L. Jackson, D. <i>Australia</i>	Maternity ward / adult ICU	To describe early mothering experiences after emergency hysterectomy for PPH.	Women who had an emergency hysterectomy following PPH (N=21)	Qualitative naturalistic inquiry	Semi-structured interviews	Difficult early mothering experiences related to lost bonding time, feelings of failure and relinquishing care of the infant, with emotional distress arising from separation and extreme concern about what was happening to the infant while they were separated. Mothers described reduced ability to care for their infant up to a year post op.
2012 Baum, N. Weidberg, Z. Osher, Y. Kohélet, D. <i>Israel</i>	NICU	To examine mothers' responses to their babies following pre-term delivery	Mothers of VLBW babies (N=30)	Qualitative, phenomenological	In-depth semi-structured interviews (3 to 9wks after delivery)	Mothers felt barely present, "not feeling like a mother", and had a sense of emptiness and longing, as the separation from their baby was abrupt.
2012 Bayes, S. Fenwick, J. Hauck, Y. <i>Australia</i>	Maternity	To explore and explain women's experiences of the day they gave birth by medically necessary c-s	Women who had elective c-s (N=28)	Grounded theory	Participant observation during c-s; field notes; retrospective semi-structured interviews (10 to 14wks after c-s)	Mothers described how operating room procedures prevented them from taking up their maternal role once the baby was born, resulting in the loss of early bonding time. Mothers gave examples of feeling disengaged and indifferent to their baby's cries after separation.

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Methodology	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2012 Hammarlund, K. Björk, M. Thelin, A. Peterson, I. <i>Sweden</i>	Neonatal ward	To describe mothers' experiences of BF a preterm infant in a neonatal ward.	Mothers of neonates <37wks (N=12)	Qualitative, descriptive	Protocol writing - mothers were asked to write a description of their lived experience.	Separation of the dyad meant that the mother didn't know when their baby was awake and needing them. Mothers described "deep loss" at not being able to be with their preterm infant, particularly at night.
2013 Akbarbegloo, M. Valizadeh, L. Asadollahi, M. <i>Iran</i>	NICU	To determine the stressors of mothers who have a premature infant in neonatal intensive care.	Mothers hospitalised with PI in NICU (N=300)	Qualitative, descriptive	PSS:NICU	60.3% mothers were stressed about being separated from their infant. Major stressors were the i) NICU environment; ii) how baby looks, behaves and treatment; and iii) relationship with baby and parent role. Subscale iii was scored significantly higher by mothers (p=0.047).
2013 Hurst, N. Engebretson, J. Mahoney, JS. <i>USA</i>	NICU	To understand the mothers' experiences of daily pumping routines during the NICU stay.	Pump-dependent mothers of very pre-term infants (N=14)	Qualitative, ethnographic approach	In-depth interviews: within 2wks following delivery and 4-6 wks once BF established.	Mothers experienced the act of pumping as both a wedge between and a connection to their infant. Some mothers found pumping therapeutic as it was something they could do for their infant.
2014 Lindgren, H. Malm, MC. Rådestad, I. <i>Sweden</i>	N/A	To investigate mothers' experiences of saying farewell to their stillborn baby.	Mothers who had suffered a still-birth (N=23)	Qualitative, descriptive	Semi-structured interviews	Mothers described distress in relation to five themes: unnatural to leave the baby; going home empty-handed; access to the child; security and insecurity in the separation; to let go. The overarching theme was: You don't leave your baby.
2015 Pennestri, MH. Gaudreau, H.	NICU	To investigate whether there was a difference in	Mother-infant dyads (N=162)	Quantitative, descriptive, longitudinal	Attachment security measured using Strange	In No NICU group 55.4% children were securely attached; 24.5% insecure and 20.1% disorganized at 36 months.

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Methodology	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
Bouvette-Turcot, AA. Moss, E. Lecompte, V. Atkinson, L. Lydon, J. Steiner, M. Meaney, MJ. <i>Canada</i>		attachment security between children who received special care at birth (NICU and/or incubator) and children who did not in full-term children.			Situation procedure at 36 months	In the NICU group 43.5% children were securely attached; 8.7% insecure and 47.8% were disorganized at 36 months. Logistic regression revealed an odds ratio of 6.1 for developing disorganised attachment after a stay in NICU, when controlling for confounding variables (p=0.003).
2016 Alves, E. Magano, R. Amorim, M. Nogueira, C. Silva, S. <i>Portugal</i>	NICU	To assess parent perceptions of factors helping or hindering providing breastmilk according to sociodemographic, reproductive, and obstetric characteristics	Parents of VPI (<32wks): 120 mothers, 91 fathers (N=211)	Qualitative, cross-sectional, observational study	Structured interviews in questionnaire format, developed from a literature review.	24.3% parents said the physical separation from the infant hindered milk supply. Physical separation from infants was primarily expressed as a hindrance to milk supply by more educated parents. Parents who used assisted reproductive technologies, those with multiple pregnancies or complications were more likely to highlight the issue of separation from the infant.
2016 Chaplin, J. Kelly, J. Kildea, S. <i>Australia</i>	BF support centre	To explore the experience of women with BF problems following a c-s under regional anaesthesia.	Women referred to hospital BF support centre (N=8)	Interpretive phenomenology	Semi-structured interviews and reflective journals	Six of the eight women reported feeling separated from and unable to help their babies (who lay in cots less than a metre away) due to their lack of ability to mobilise following the anaesthesia.

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Methodology	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2016 Ikonen, R. Paavilainen, E. Kaunonen, M. <i>Finland</i>	NICU	To describe mothers' experiences with expressing breast milk for preterm or SGA infants	Mothers of premature or SGA infants (N=130)	Qualitative, descriptive	Internet-based open-ended questionnaire	69.2% of mothers considered milk expression helpful and necessary to manage their situation, and sometimes the only positive action they could take for their baby.
2017 Gulla, K. Dahlø, R. Eilertsen, MEB. <i>Norway</i>	NICU	To explore mothers' experiences with SSC during hospitalisation following birth.	Mothers of moderately premature infants (32 to 34wks) (N=9)	Qualitative exploratory	Retrospective focus groups	While the hospital staff described mothers' access to their infants as unrestricted, numerous practical and logistical obstacles were described. Barriers to SSC included: lack of comfortable chairs for mothers, lack of space and uncertainty regarding the mother's (unlimited) access to NICU.
2017 Mukwenda, AM. Mbekenga, CK. Pembe, AB. Olsson, P. <i>Tanzania</i>	"Semi-intensive care unit"	To explore and describe women's experiences of having had and recovered from eclampsia at a tertiary hospital.	Mothers recovering from eclampsia (N=10)	Qualitative, descriptive	Semi-structured interviews	Mothers accommodated separately to their babies encountered physical barriers to their presence due to the hospital environment. Mothers reported distress and anxiety due to separation, compounded by not knowing what was happening to their baby or how it was being cared for.
2017 Sankar, V, Batra, P. Saroja, M. Sadiza, J. <i>India</i>	NICU	To assess parental satisfaction with traditional systems of NICU care	Parents of late preterm/term infants (N=100)	Cross-sectional study	Semi-structured interviews and questionnaires	Among parents able to see their baby once a day with minimal involvement, over two fifths expressed dismay at not being able to look after their own baby; just over one third expressed discontent at not being able to BF their baby. Even though parents were only able to see their babies once a day with minimal involvement, parents scored a 77.75% satisfaction in the "parental involvement" section.

UK United Kingdom, NICU neonatal intensive care unit, VPI very preterm infants, PI premature infants, PSS parent stressor scale, VLBW very low birthweight, c-s caesarean section, VAMS visual analogue mood scale, ICU intensive care unit, PPH post-partum haemorrhage, BF breastfeeding, HCP healthcare professionals, SGA small for gestational age, SARS severe acute respiratory syndrome

Table 2. Summary of evidence from intervention studies

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Intervention type and duration	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2005 Mörelius, E. Theodorsson, E. & Nelson, N. <i>Sweden</i>	NICU	To investigate how SSC influences stress for the mother and the infant in NICU.	Mother-infant pairs (N=17)	Individuals acted as their own controls before, during, and after SSC on two different occasions (first and fourth SSC).	Mothers: salivary cortisol, HR, mood scale, and stress (VAS). Infants: salivary cortisol, HR and pain (NIPP and NIPS).	Mother self-rated stress (VAS) decreased significantly in SSC. Mother salivary cortisol and HR also decreased during SSC, but the change reached significance only after SSC was completed. Infant pain and HR decreased during SSC. Infant cortisol was significantly higher at the first SSC than at the fourth SSC, when the infants were clinically more stable. Infants were more relaxed and had a deeper sleep during both the first and the fourth SSC as reflected by their HR and behavioural state.
2011 Morgan, BE. Horn, AR. Bergman, NJ. <i>South Africa</i>	Postnatal ward	To investigate the impact of MNS.	Full-term, 2-day old neonates (N=16)	Within group study design comparing HRV in infants sleeping in SSC and sleeping alone (x 1hr each).	Level of arousal – Anderson Behavioural State Scale; IBI and HRV (VU-AMS device)	MNS was associated with a dramatic increase in HRV power (increase of 176% in autonomic activity). MNS had a negative impact on quiet sleep duration (reduction of 86% in quiet sleep).

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Intervention type and duration	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2013 Gabriel, MAM. de Mendoza, BdrH. Figuroa, LJ. Medina, V. Fernández, Bl. Rodríguez, MV. Huedo, VE. Malagón, LM. <i>Spain</i>	Maternity ward	To investigate the analgesic effect (measured by NIPS) of BF in addition to SSC vs other methods of non-pharm analgesia during heel lance.	Term neonates (N=136. 35 BF & SSC, 35 sucrose & SSC, 33 SSC and 33 sucrose)	RCT Grp 1: Infants BF and SSC, Grp 2: Infants given sucrose and in SSC, Grp 3: Infants in SSC, Grp 4: Infants given sucrose	Pain scores on NIPS: T0 - 2min before heel lance, T1 - heel lance, T2 - 2min after heel lance	BF with SSC was associated with significantly lower pain scores compared to other forms of non -pharmaceutical analgesia tested.
2014 Dearn, T. Shoemark, H. <i>Australia</i>	Special care nursery	To determine the effect of maternal presence on the physiological and behavioural status of the preterm infant when exposed to recorded music vs ambient sound.	Clinically stable preterm infants >28wks, enrolled at >32wks, and their mothers (N=22 dyads. 10 experimental group and 12 control group)	Repeated measures RCT. Experimental: Infants exposed to lullaby music with and without mothers present. Control group: infants exposed to lullaby music twice while mothers absent.	Infant behavioural state (Thoman's (1990) primary states taxonomy), SpO2 and mean HR.	Infants' physiological and behavioural regulation were affected by the presence and departure of their mothers, with maternal presence having a beneficial physiological effect on infants' HR, SpO2 and behavioural state. Infants displayed increased SpO2 when mothers were present (p=0.024), despite mothers being uninvolved (only present) for 63% of the time and spent less time in quiet sleep after mothers' departure.

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the study	Sample	Intervention type and duration	Data collection methods	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2016 Chi Luong, K. Long Nguyen, T. Thi, H. Huong, D. Carrara, HP. Bergman, N. <i>Vietnam</i>	Neonatal & maternity units	To compare the effects of SSC and the conventional method of care (involving maternal infant separation) on the stabilisation of newly born LBW infants (Replication of Bergman et al 2004).	Mother-infant dyads (N=100. 50 SSC and 50 conventional care)	Intervention: infants in SSC & BF. Control: mothers and infants separated as per hospital protocol (infant in an incubator or cot and fed formula milk).	SCRIP (HR, RR and SpO2 monitored continuously during a 5min period). Blood glucose at 180 and 360 minutes.	Total SCRIP score was significantly greater in the SSC group at 120 min (5.66 ± 0.72 vs 4.72 ± 0.83 , $p < 0.0001$) and at 360 min ($p = 0.0001$), with a significant temporal trend over 6 hours ($p = 0.02$). Beyond 6hrs, SSC infants required less IV fluid (6/50 vs 26/50, $p < 0.001$) and less antibiotic use (9/50 vs 26/50, $p = 0.004$). Separated infants had respiratory instability during the first three or four hours, followed by HR instability up to six hours. Separated infants also experienced bradycardia, decreased respiratory rate, lower temperature, and decreased blood glucose.
2017 Kerr, S. King, C. Hogg, R. McPherson, K. Hanley, J. Brierton, M. Ainsworth, S. <i>UK</i>	NNU	To explore parent and professional views of the impact of the Mylittleone technology.	Parents of babies admitted to NNU (N=33. 25 moms and 8 dads). HCP working in NNU (N=18) – <i>HCP data not included in results</i>	Mylittleone technology transmits real-time images of the baby via a webcam from the NNU to the mother's bedside in the post-natal care environment.	Semi-structured, face to face interviews	Benefits of the real-time images centred on: enhanced feelings of closeness; increased physical responsiveness (breastmilk production); emotional wellbeing; and focused physical recovery. Technology bridged the gap of physical separation.

SSC skin to skin contact, LBW low birth-weight, RCT randomised controlled trial, SCRIP stability of cardio-respiratory system in preterm infants, HR heart rate, RR respiratory rate, BF breastfed, c-s caesarean section, PACU post-anaesthesia care unit, BF breastfeeding, KMC Kangaroo Mother Care, NIPP Neonatal Infant Pain Profile, NIPS Neonatal Infant Pain Scale, MNS maternal-neonatal separation, IBI inter-beat intervals, HRV heart rate variability, VU-AMS VU University Ambulatory Monitoring System

Table 3. Summary of review/discussion papers

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the review/discussion	Scope	Methodology	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2003 Nelson, AM. USA	Postnatal	To synthesize the results of nine qualitative studies related to the transition to motherhood to provide cumulative insights into the need for future program development.	Nine qualitative studies related to the transition to motherhood were included in the final meta-synthesis.	Noblit and Hare's (1988) meta-ethnographic, comparative method.	Engagement is the basic process present in maternal transition. Rooming-in on the postpartum floor and KMC in the NICU are interventions that promote maternal engagement. Engagement of the mothers to come to know and care for their infants should be facilitated.
2014 Olza-Fernández, I. Marín Gabriel, MA. Gil-Sanchez, A. Garcia-Segura, LM. Arevalo, MA. Spain	Postnatal	To describe the hormonal cascade in the maternal and the newborn brain, at parturition, the early postpartum period and lactation, which primes the mother and the newborn for attachment initiation and consolidation.	Not stated	Not stated	The bonding process between a mother and her preterm infant is impaired by separation (caused by admission to NICU). Therefore, the neuroendocrine changes that are associated with mother-child synchrony are not elicited. Newborns separated from their mothers have worse mother-child interaction one year after birth. The stress of prolonged mother-infant separation is also associated with reduced maternal sensitivity and more negative patterns of mothering throughout the first 3 years of life.
2015 Groer, MW. Gregory, KE. Louis-Jacques, A. Thibeau, S. Walker, WA.	Postnatal units	To describe current understanding of the nature of the microbiome of the very low birthweight infant	Descriptive review of the current literature	Not stated	Influences on the infant's microbiome include delivery by c-s/vaginal birth; antibiotics (infant and mother); BF and SSC. The use of the mother's own milk should be priority for every NICU. SSC provides microbial transfer and separation of the mother and infant should be avoided to prevent interruption of the

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the review/discussion	Scope	Methodology	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
USA					mother's microbiome to the infant. Antibiotics should only be used when necessary.
2015 Mylod, D. UK	Postnatal units	To summarise current understandings in relation to BF sick children in hospital, in the context of a social media campaign.	Discussion of literature and current policy recommendations	Not stated	Evidence draws clear bridges between exclusive BF and the prevention and reduction of a myriad of infections and conditions. Highlights literature which states that SSC as a routine practice to facilitate BF initiation is impeded by the physical separation of mother and baby, medical equipment and treatment, the baby's health, and a lack of privacy in a high-risk clinical environment.
2016 Boykova, M USA	NICU and maternity	To summarize and synthesize the available literature (1980–2014) related to the experiences and needs of parents who had their preterm infants hospitalized and discharged home.	Fifty selected (37 quantitative and 13 qualitative) reports of research conducted on parents of preterm infants during 1980–2014 were included.	Whittemore and Knalf's framework for integrative reviews.	The disruption of bonding at the beginning of the infant's life and mother's discharge home (and therefore separation) without the infant create a feeling of "not being a parent" as reported in several reviewed studies. Parents of preterm infants are at risk for developing strained relationships with their infants because of the absence of the normal beginning of parenthood and altered parent role during hospitalisation.
2016 D'Agata, AL. Young, EE. Cong, XM. Grasso, DJ. McGrath, JM. USA	NICU	To provide rationale for the concept of Infant Medical Trauma in the NICU (IMTN).	Documentary sources: 106 published papers cited.	Research synthesis of published evidence to present a conceptual model for IMTN	Stress and allostasis: IMTN comprises a triad of cumulative early life NICU experiences (stress, parental separation, and pain) which are held to influence outcomes (risk and resilience) through their impact on an infant's swinging neurodevelopment. Combination of stress, parental separation and pain contribute negatively to allostatic load, increasing the vulnerability and the risk for poorer outcomes.

Year, Author and Country	Setting	Aims of the review/discussion	Scope	Methodology	Key findings relevant to mother-child separation
2016 Moore, E. R. Bergman, N. Anderson, G. C. Medley, N. <i>UK (Cochrane)</i>	Maternity	To assess the effects of immediate or early SSC on healthy newborn infants and their mothers compared to standard contact.	RCTs that compared SSC to standard, hospitalized care (N=38 trials with 3472 women and infants)	Systematic review conducted according to Cochrane methodology	SSC infants had higher SCRIP scores, suggesting better stabilisation on three physiological parameters; higher blood glucose levels and similar temperature to infants in standard care (all trials graded low quality).

USA United State of America, NICU neonatal intensive care unit, c-s caesarean section, BF breastfeeding, SSC skin-to-skin contact, KMC kangaroo mother care, SCRIP stability of cardio-respiratory system in preterm infants